

SCHOOL ACCEPTANCE TOWARD STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS - CASE STUDY IN SMP TAMAN DEWASA IBU PAWIYATAN YOGYAKARTA, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

The objectives of this research were to find out the school acceptance toward students with special needs and factors which affect the acceptance in SMP Taman Dewasa Ibu Pawiyatan Yogyakarta. This research used qualitative approach with case study. The subjects, 23 regular students, 10 teachers, and the Headmaster of SMP (Junior High School) Taman Dewasa, were chosen purposively and snowball sampling. Data collection techniques were in-depth interviews, participant observation, and documentation. Triangulation data validity used as source and technique even negative case analyze. Data analysis were data reduction, data display, and conclusion. The research finding is an acceptance attitude based on: (a) the students were making a classmate and involving work groups, being close friends, and being the partners in activities; (b) the teachers were giving equal social treatment, having close relationships, involving the class activities, giving attention, and greetings; and (c) the Headmaster gave the greeting, protecting, and maintaining the school environment. The acceptance factors that related to the students with special need: no physical oddities, clothes and behavior according to the school environment, potentially, positive personality, and controlling emotions. Other acceptance factors which were not related to the students with special needs: first impressions, high empathy, positive personality, good mindset and expectation, status and the parents doctrine, and no jealousy of regular students.

Keywords: school acceptance, acceptance factors, students with special needs.

1. Introduction

Students with special needs interact with the school environments, students, teachers, headmasters, and staffs, to get new attitude experiences based on the interactions they

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had done. Thurstone, he formulates attitudes as the degree of positive affects or negative affects on a psychological object (Edwards in Syafrida Elisa and Aryani Tri Wrastari, 2013: 3). Heri Purwanto also explained that a positive attitude is the tendency of action in the form of approaching, enjoying, and expecting a particular object. While a negative attitude is a tendency to avoid, avoid, hate, dislike certain objects (in Syafrida Elisa and Aryani Tri Wrastari, 2013: 3).

Human, as an individual living, must adapt to the values in their surroundings. If someone does not comply with the values in his environment, it can result a rejection (Dian Ibing, 2009: 54). Being rejected and being ignored by the peers will lead to the emergence of loneliness and hostility (Desmita, 2005: 221).

School acceptance can be initiated from the school's openness to accept students with special needs. Students with special needs are also considered to have positive values to be involved in the education process. The school is called as an inclusive school. Inclusive schools provide benefits not only beneficial to the students with special needs but also the students as a whole and the surrounding community.

However, based on the result of the studies conducted by the government shows that the low public awareness for the fulfillment of children with special needs compared with regular children. Some people in the community tend to put the children with special needs away from the social community, education, and ignoring their potential development (taken from <http://nttprov.go.id>). Children with special needs are also vulnerable to discrimination and violence. "*Discrimination towards children with special needs and minority children are considered as regular,*" said Susanto (Commissioner of the Commission for the Protection of Indonesian Children) to be seen as a common practice in educating children. (Karta Raharja Ucu, 2015). In addition to the coalition spokesman, Hari Kurniawan (Eko Widiyanto, 2012) said, "*some educational institutions do not care and ignore their rights*".

Violent cases toward children with special needs occurred in several region, school and special needs children's dormitories in Santa Maria Imaculata, East Jakarta. TH as the parents of a children with special needs (initials SAH) found his son got bruised, burns on both soles of his feet, and injured in the genitals. SAH is experiencing an unstable emotional disturbance. SAH was immediately rushed to the Immanuel Hospital Bandung and treated for 10 days after the incident. TH reported the school to National Child Protection Commission for what they have done on March 19, 2014 and Polrestro East Jakarta, on March 25, 2014 (Warta Kota, June 9, 2014).

Answering to the issues, inclusive education should be the best solution against discriminatory attitudes of particular groups. Basically, inclusive education will give no spaces between students with special needs, with other regular students. They will work together in the same school environment. The meaning of inclusiveness also will change the mindset of the community in accepting the special needs children which will be considered as well as regular children.

SMP (Junior High School) Taman Dewasa Ibu Pawiyatan Yogyakarta is one of the inclusive school in Yogyakarta. The school is willingly to accept the students with

special needs along with their potentials to be well educated as regular students in Senior High School. The school also appreciating the individual values that the special students needs have.

In 2008, the school began to have the title as an inclusive school based on the governments' recommendation. SMP Taman Dewasa Ibu Pawiyatan Yogyakarta is a school initiated by Ki Hadjar Dewantara in 1922 (education figure in Indonesia). Apparently, Tamansiswa, the concept of education which carried by Ki Hadjar related to the concept of inclusive education. Ki Hadjar Dewantara's concept is not only focused on the students' intellectual but also the values of the people, the culture, the character and the nation.

There is a relationship between education of Tamansiswa and inclusive education. Tamansiswa emphasize the importance of education in accordance with the nature of the child so that teachers only lead the development of the talent. Therefore it will be a students learning centered. Each student has different needs and the teacher's role is as a facilitator in meeting the needs of the students and developing their abilities. The researcher is interested to explore more information about school admission of students with special needs. This study is expected to provide an explanation of the attitudes of acceptance given by the school along with the factors that led to the attitude.

2. Literatue Review

2.1 Child with Special Needs

Hallahan dan Kauffman (Edi Purwanta, 2012: 54) describe a child with special needs is "*... those who require special education and related service if they are to realize their full human potential*". Kirk dan Gallagher (Muljono Abdurrachman dan Sudjaji, 1994: 9) also define special children as children who deviate from average or normal in: (1) mental characteristics, (2) sensory abilities, (3) neuromotor or physical characteristics, (4) social behavior, (5) communication skills, and (6) combinations of various the variable. Based on expert opinion above, it can be concluded that children with special needs are children who have certain needs in the form of various difficulties in academic and development that are unique and different from normal children in general. These difficulties can be caused from internal and external factors that influence the development that is not optimal so that it requires special services to achieve optimal development.

2.2 Acceptance

Cecil G. Osorne (2001: 31) explains that acceptance is the answer or the acceptance of a person in a community members, whether family, ethnic group, nation, or other social group. According to Chaplin psychology dictionary (2004: 4), acceptance is a positive attitude characterized by the recognition or appreciation of individual values without including recognition of his behavior or without emotional relationship attachment.

While the acceptance of the peers is defined as the chosen friends or the group members to follow the group activities. It shows that acceptance means recognizing the positive values of someone which is realizing through involving someone in an individual activity or group activity.

Bernard says (in Andi Mappiare, 1982: 144) the needs of a teenager in the secondary school are the needs of self adjustment in the peer group, the adjustment of teachers, the adjustment in the parent-teacher-student relationship, the provision or clarity of goals, the stability of self-esteem, self-understanding, and the preparation for marriage. Adjustment in "peer" will expose a teenager to the issue of peer rejection and acceptance. Rejection is a very disappointing thing for teenagers.

Acceptance can make a person feel being appreciated and being needed. Hurlock (1978: 297) states that a positive impact if the individual is accepted by his or her social group are to have a positive self-concept, have more opportunities to participate in peer group activities, have a good social awareness, and know how to make friend.

3. Material and Methods

Qualitative approach was used in the research with case study method. This research was conducted at SMP Taman Dewasa Ibu Pawiyatan Yogyakarta which is located in Jl. Tamansiswa No. 25 F, Wirogunan, Mergangsan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Research subjects are 23 regular students, 7 occupied teachers, 3 teachers who are concurrently employees, and the Headmaster of SMP Taman Dewasa purposively selected and are snowball sampling. The data collection techniques are in-depth interviews, participant observation, and a documentation study of school admission to students with special needs. The research instrument is the researcher himself. The validity of the data using triangulation technique and negative case analysis. Data is analyzed through reduction data, presentation data, and conclusion.

4. Result and Discussion

School acceptance is a socially acceptable attitude embodied in the form of recognition of a positive value to a person and seeks to involving a person in the school activities. Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, it is known that the school admission forms are listed in the following table.

Table 1: Acceptance of Students toward Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
Students' attitude during the learning activities	- Decide as a seatmate
	- Decide as workmate
	- As close friends
	- Asking for a chit-chat

Given assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Helping in understanding the lesson and school activities - Reminding if crossing the line - Understands the needs of students with special needs - Give supports
Students' attitude outside the learning activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Making conversation and making jokes - Hanging out together (went to the canteen, library, friends' house, shopping mall) - Classroom agenda: arisan - Doing a collective activities (drawing, playing, school outbond)

The revenue of students with special needs by the teacher and the staffs' happens during the learning activities and outside the learning activities.

Table 2: Teachers Acceptance toward Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
Social treatment compared with the regular students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Treat the students with special needs equal with the normal students - Reminding and give suitable punishments if it is necessary - No different treatment unless they want it - The different learning approach
Teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Asking questions - No social discrimination - Having fun and chit-chats - Treat them as their own children - Give supports - Being knowledable of the students
Getting involved in a classroom activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involved in a group work with the help of the teacher - Involved in a competition and calassroom activities based on the students' skill
Special attention from the teacher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Approaching the students, asking and giving help - during the lesson - Giving chance to answer questions
Special attention from the teacher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Put the deaf students sitting down in the front row during the class - Facilitate the students during practicum lesson - Reminding to bring the lesson book - Giving suggestion for the next degree
Teacher acceptance outside the classroom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greet each other - Giving smile - Asking for chit-chats (asking for condition and situation) - Make jokes

Otherwise, Headmasters' acceptance towards the students with special needs is listed in this following table.

Table 3: Headmasters' Acceptance toward the Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
Headmasters acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Giving smile - Greet the students - Giving protection to the students if there is unpleasant attitude towards them - Reminding the students if it is necessary

Based on the above table, it is known that some students, teachers, employees, and the headmaters accept the students with special needs in the school activities. This is evidenced by the social activities of students with special needs together with regular students such as forming work groups in the classroom and activities outside the classroom. Cecil (2001: 30) says that acceptance is the answer of a person being accepted in a community group, whether family, tribe, nation, or other social groups.

Teachers and employees acceptance showed by involving the students with special needs in the classroom activities. Lay Kekeh Marthan (2007: 142) says, inclusive education provides equal opportunities between students with special needs with regular students in one class with the same quality of education. This means that all students get the same attention in inclusive schools. Teachers provide understanding to regular students to better understand the characteristics of students with special needs so that the students can get along together. What the teacher had done, it can help the students with special needs being accepted in their peers.

The teacher tries to get closer to the students with special needs. Prayitno explains the internalized proximity between educators and learners are being sincere, open acceptance, characterized by a willingness to accept and give, freedom of expression, freedom of movement, warm atmosphere, and clarity of direction, and other means that can be taken by all parties in the proximity (2009: 98).

Attitudes shown by the teachers, employees, students, and Headmaster above are a positive attitude in the form of appreciating, loving, and enjoyed with an object so there is a willingness to perform activities with the object. Heri Purwanto states that a positive attitude is the tendency of an action in the form of approaching, enjoying, and expecting a particular object. (in Syafrida Elisa and Aryani Tri Wrastari, 2013: 3). Prayitno (2009: 125) states that the affections and tenderness of an educator can be actualized through: a) greeting such as greet, call, say greeting, and rebuke with sweet, fresh and spirit; b) a positive response in polite ways and with good words; c) the appearance of sympathy and empathy displayed through the behavior of tenderness with speech, writing, touch, and other expressions; d) speech with reasonable intonation, sound pressure, and rhythm; with the selected words; and a polite and respectful attitude; and e) a genuine solicitation and encouragement. This means both of the teacher and the Headmaster love and care about the students with special needs.

Acceptance can generate confidence and dare to interact with regular students and teachers. Researchers found the following attitude.

Table 4: Benefits of Admission for Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
The emerge of students with special needs' confident	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brave to come to the front of the class - Dare to ask friends when have difficulties in lesson - Brave to buy foods on his own - Having dreams and wishes
Able to interact with the teacher and regular students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dare to share stories - Please in communication - Playing and talks - Friendly - Care about friends (giving massage, help, and buy foods) - Joking - Try to have teacher's attention

Dedy Kustawan (2012: 10) explains that the benefits of inclusive education for learners with special needs are to increase their self-reliance, confidence, and provide opportunities to adjust to the environment in general. Adjustment to the environment will provide students with special needs to interact with regular students. The successful of an interaction can be seen in the students interactions with the peers. The cause of a successful adjusment are the acceptance and understands that a students with special needs as a unique individual therefore it can influence the student itself yo be more confident.

Acceptance is influenced by several factors. Researchers share the factors that come from self and outside the self-need students. Factors from the self-need of special students will increase or decrease the acceptance shown in the following table.

Table 5: Factors from Self-Needed Students with Special Needs Improving Reception

Aspect	Data
Physically the same with the regular students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Melancholy eyesight - Daydreaming often - Seeing intensely - Can be recognized through looking at the face
Physically different with the regular students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hands and foot are imperfect - Different facial expressions - The pupil moves instable
The uniform suits with the school rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wearing the uniform tidily - never wearing improper uniform
Cooperatrion and responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - group cooperation (bring the group equipments, looking for the answer of the given questions) - being responsible to the individual work

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - responsibility toward others (helping friends, paying the treasury, bring the assigned work of the group)
Cooperation and responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - self responsibility (done the homework, do the housework, ironing, cleaning the room, sweeping the floor)
Choosig polite words	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - able to use the appropriate words in having a talk with the tacher and friends
Special potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DR (initial) is good at drawing, computer, fast typing, being obedient - YH (initial) is good at drawing - D (initial) is able to read and memorizing Al Qur'an (Juz 1-3, 30, surah An Naba, adzan) - FE (initial) is talented in drawing, won a fashion show competition, reading Al Qur'san - MD (initial) is good at studying, singing, playing music, drawing caricature - AY (initial) is able to read Al-Qur'an.
Positive personality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being honest - Easy to imitate others opinion - Being honest, giving back the lost things that they found - Open to share what they feel
Aspect	Data
Positive personality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tell the teacher about the teacher they dislike and the reason of not making friends with students with special needs - Willingly to answer an interview

Meanwhile, the decreasing of students acceptance can be seen in the following table.

Table 6: Self Decreasing Factors by the Students with a Special Needs

Aspect	Data
Inappropriate school uniform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inappropriate in wearing the uniform - Untidy when wearing veil - Rarely ironed uniform - Smelly uniform
Less-responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Irresponsible such as not paying the treasury
Impolite	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being noisy during the lesson - Laughing when the friends being warned - Calling <i>pak</i> (Mr.) instead of <i>mas</i> (Mr.)
Social interaction: alone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eating alone in the school break time - Sitting down alone when break time - Being alone when break time
The interactions among the students with a special need	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Having a chit-chat in the middle of break time

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sitting down together - buy foods together - Playing handphone - Go to pendopo and other places with the friends
Immature emotional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harsh to the friends - Lie and angry - Easy to spill the beans - Inappropriate talk - Glummy - Angry when the friends making jokes - Crying until loosing control - Say rude words - Pornography
Negative personality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being arrogant when have a new friend - Being stingy when the friend is trying to borrow his stuffs - Lazy to do sports activities - Childish

4.1 Other the Acceptance Factors that Related to Students with Special Needs

a. Physical Appearance

The absence of physical oddities makes students with special needs have more chances of getting friends. Although physically they look the same without any lack or meaningful difference, it does not affect the school acceptance. Hurlock (in Rita Eka Izzaty, et al, 2008: 142) says that one of the factors that influence adolescent social acceptance is the self appearance in accordance with the appearance of peers. Karl and Joels (in Kun Maryati and Juju Suryawati, 2001: 66) argue that the source of information about a person in social interactions such as skin color, sex, physical appearance, body shape, clothing, and discourse. Physical appearance is the first thing that is generally seen by others.

It is a different matter, less perfect, with some of the students who questioned the physical appearance of a students with speacial needs with the regular students. Lack of understanding factors and attitudinal factors of students with special needs that are less appropriate so that regular students are too focused on the physical needs of students with special needs, can be the reason students are less able to accept them

b. Clothing and How to Dress

The teacher often praises the appearance of the students with special needs who tend to be well dressed according to the school's environment. Dian Ibung (2009: 54) said that praise is an example of a positive reaction given to a person because his/ her behavior has been in accordance with the values in the environment so that it can be motivated to strengthen the behavior that is praised. Someone will get a respect from other due to the way the get dresses, such as young executives get more respect than people who dresses carelessly. (Karl and Yoels in Kun Maryati and Juju Suryawati, 2001: 66).

However, some students with special needs deviates from the arranged uniform. Regular students make the issue because it causes inconvenience in socializing. Students with special needs who do not appear in accordance with their environment means not in accordance with the values adopted by the group resulting in negative reaction from the group.

c. Social Behavior of Students with Special Needs

Some students with special needs can work with regular students. The student consists of several slow learner, mentally handicaped, and autism students. Because students with special needs can be invited to work together after a clear division of tasks so many students who enjoy especially in the division of group tasks so that the task becomes lighter. Hurlock (in Rita Eka Izzaty, et al, 2008: 142) states that a sporty and pleasant soul and good social behavior such as cooperation, responsibility, long-mindedness, shared with others, wisdom, and being polite will affect a person's acceptance.

However, sometimes students with special needs tend to work with fellow students with special needs. Some students of mentally handicaped and slow learner are speech less, more passive, or often joked in group collaboration. This corresponds to their character that is sometimes shy or reserved but will change if they are included to interact with other children (Frieda Mangunsong, 2014: 132). Mumpuniarti (2000: 41-44) describes a child with mild mentally handicaped capable of doing a simple work. As for slow learner students, one of the obstacles in social interaction is how slow to receive information because of the limitations of receptive and expressive language. Therefore, there should be a clear division in group work, especially for autistic students so that the students can engage in cooperation.

The next factor is responsibility. The responsibilities which had done can create trust and appreciation among the students with a special needs and regular students so they will be needed in the environment. Students with special needs who have low ability in responsibilities are less appreciated by the regular students. Students feel disappointed, annoyed and less respect for students with special needs that affect the interaction in acceptance.

Some students with special needs are able to show the polite and courteous attitude that is seen from the proper selection of words in communicating with the teacher and friends. This indicates that students with special needs are able to harmonize with the values adopted by the environment. Dian Ibung (2009: 54) states that the first time they will adjust the moral values they have gained before with the moral values of his peers.

Meanwhile, regular students do not like the attitude of students with special needs which is as a slow learner and mild mentally handicaped that tend like to disturb and mock others. Some regular students mock students with special needs by calling them "ABK" (Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus/Student with Special Need), mocking with inappropriate words, even throwing or beating them. This is because, the behavior of

students with special needs is less in accordance with environmental values so that regular students do not like it. According to Sri Rumini (1980: 57), one of the characteristics of slow learner students are like to talk more and talk about concrete things than learning. Mentally handicapped students often laugh at a friend or call a teacher with a poor designation due to his underdeveloped emotions. Tin Suharmini (2009: 88) states, the emotions of child mentally handicapped is not mature enough, sometimes still looks like emotions in childhood, visible clear, easily influenced, sensitive, and sometimes over reactive.

Some regular students also having a lack interaction with students with special needs. Students with special needs such as several students with mentally handicapped, slow learner, and deaf, tend to interact socially with fellow students with special needs or solitude. Nani Triani and Amir (2013: 12-13) explains that slow learner children have low social interaction skills such as choosing to be passive players or with drawing and prefer to play with children under the age of feeling safer with communication using simple language. Some children also show their sense of humor. This is what causes the students with special needs more comfortable to make friends with students with special needs.

A deaf students tend to be an individual, therefore most of regular students does not try to make friends with them. One reason, the deaf student also has a self-concept that is less precise because they think that they are being mean to others because often being alone. Tin Suharmini (2009: 84) explains that the misperception of some of the communication done by deaf children in their interactions, plus unpleasant responses, often leads to misunderstandings and emotional distress. Emotional pressure shows angry, irritable, restless, anxious, easy to get insulted, acting aggressively, or withdrawing and hesitating. Therefore, because of the emotions that appear quickly, deaf students experience problems of self-concept and prefer to be alone in interactions.

d. Students with Special Needs Have Special Potential

Regular students enjoy making friends with students with special needs with special potential. Edi Purwanta (2012: 60-61) define that students with special needs vary in their potential, one of them is emphasize in the potential (including already shown up and not yet). Regular students can engage students with special needs in activities they have already mastered such as drawing, memorizing the Qur'an, or singing.

e. The Personality of Students with Special Needs

Some students of mentally handicapped and slow learner are welcome to others. Frieda Mangunsong (2014: 131 - 134) explains that mild mentally handicapped students sometimes show shyness and being quiet but it will change when they are involved in an activities with others. This openness affects teachers and students to get to know and understand better towards students with special needs so they can make the right attitude including acceptance.

Meanwhile, regular students are less fond of self-centered deaf students (individualist) and less concerned about the environment. According to Permanarian Somad and Tati Hernawati (1995: 34-39), hearing impairment can cause students to become away from in daily life which results in the inhibition of the child's maturity development. The effect of such alienation raises the attitude of egocentrism in the self-tunarugu children beyond the normal child. According to Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI) egocentrism is defined as the nature and behavior that always make onerself as the center of everythings.

f. Emotional Maturity

Some students with mild mental disorder, slow learner, and autism are lacking in emotional control to get low acceptance from the environment. Hurlock (in Rita Eka Izzaty et al, 2008: 142) states that one of the factors affecting adolescent social acceptance is maturity especially in emotional control and willingness to follow group rules. Some slow learner students become angry and snarling a friend. Nani Triani (2013: 11) explains that the emotions of slow learner students are easy to get angry, explosive and sensitive because of less stable emotions.

4.2 Other the Acceptance Factors that Not Related to Students with Special Need

Some of the mental disorder students speak impolite and being rude to their friends. For students with mild mental disorder, the psychological condition felt is difficult to think both abstractly and logically, less able to analyze, associate, have fantasy, control feelings, easily influenced, have a good personality because they are less able to assess good and bad things (Mumpuniarti, 2000 : 41). Mental disorder students also have high sex lust, and it is difficult to control themselves (Maria J. Wantah, 2007: 15). The case of pornographic video storage in mild mental disorder students is because of a strong sex lust while students are unable to control it.

Some autistic students are able to respond to a thing excessively. Autism is associated with sensory disorders such as frequent anger for obscure reasons, tantrums, occasional attacks, and sudden mood changes (Galih A Veskarisyanti, 2008: 20).

Besides, factors from the outside of students with special needs such as regular students, teachers, employees, Headmasters, and parents of the students with special needs that are considered to affect acceptance that occurs to him. The first impression, empathy, personality, mindset, hope, social jealousy, and influence of parents are classified as factors from the outside. First impressions and empathy forms are listed in these following tables.

Table 7: First Impeession and Emphaty factors towards Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
First impression student's emphaty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feeling nothing - Feeling difficult to learn - Feeling lees confident - Pity for haing to friends - Want to interact together - Respect other people by not mocking and comparing - Defend when logged and rejected in a workgroup - Generous and do not mind his attitude
Students' emphaty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engaging in groups - Helping to do tasks - Inquire deeply the life of the students with special needs - Make close friends and always be reminder
Teachers' and employees' emphaty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be grateful to be granted a child who do not have a disorder - Be proud to educate students with special needs - Teach with whole heart because it considers as a charity - Chatting and helping to overcome her difficulty
Teachers' and employees' emphaty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minggle with students with special needs - Invite students with special needs more recognize himself - Buy them some foods
Teachers' and employees' emphaty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do not differentiate students - Appoint students with special needs to guide other students to read the Qur'an - Invite regular students to understand students with special needs - Do not underestimated - Easy to give permission to the students
Headmaster's emphaty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compassionate to the students with special needs - Likes and be close to students with special needs - Be open with anyone

a. The First Impressions of Regular Students to Students with Special Needs

Feeling as normally and accustomed to accept the existence of students with special needs in the school environment is the key to the formation of acceptance. Hurlock (in Rita Eka Izzaty et al, 2008: 142) states that one of the factors that influence adolescent social acceptance is first impression as a result of attractive appearance as well as calm and pleasant attitude.

b. Students, Teachers, Employees, and Headmaster Have Empathy

Student empathy is shown by accepting and treating students with special needs. The teacher's empathy is capable of generating a sense of gratitude to appreciate more about the condition and try to give the best treatment to the students with special needs as a form of caring. Headmaster's empathy makes him appreciating and cherishing the students with special needs. Johnson (Aris Tri Ochtia Sari, et al., In Nunung Irawati, 2015: 9) explains that an empathist is described as someone that is being tolerant, self-controlling, friendly, influential, and humanistitarian.

c. The Students, Teachers, Employees, and Headmaster Personality

The personality that influences high acceptance is listed in the following table.

Table 8: The Students, Teachers, Employees, and Headmaster Personality

Aspect	Data
Students' Personality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Making friends with everyone - Being able to work with others - Respect others (invite to talk, greet, and respond) - Helping their friends - Not being angry easily and sad - Being friendly and sociable - Being polite and cheerful - Correct if someone did it wrong
Teachers' and Employees' personality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Treating students the same - Loving, friendly - Easy to communicate - Offer a help to solve students' difficulties - Attention, firmly - Easy to interact with students - Want to understand the students' conditions - Correct if someone did it wrong - Understand the students' skill and potential - Think positively to others - Be patience, close to students
Headmaster's Personality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be open - Be close to others - Accepting students with all conditions

A loving, affable, affirmative personality, willing to understand the students' situations, think positively to others, and openness from the members of the school is a determining factor of acceptance. Implementation of inclusive education has implications for the provision of education in high schools and vocational schools, such as schools should be more open, child-friendly, and non-discriminatory. (Dedy Kustawan, 2012: 40).

d. The Mindset

Information about students' mindset are explained in table below.

Table 9: The Regular Student's Mindset towards Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
Making Friends with students with special needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initiate to make friends - Understand well if distinguishing friends raises social resentment - Taking pity and fear what if students with special needs has no friends - Want to know more about students with special needs' world
Understanding School's Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School registered students with special needs as a whole unit as other regular students so the acceptance is a must.
Understanding needs of students with special needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students with special needs, needs an environment which allows students to interact in order to improve their self-confidence. - Compassionate and help students with special needs with whole heart.
Understanding needs of students with special needs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students with special needs is weak in both mental and physical. - Some students with special needs, need a special tutors to guide them understanding academical stuff.
Understanding How to Interact with students with special needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Appreciating - Approaching - Talking to, giving some jokes - Be able to behave actively - Being polite by lowered the voice - Protecting, loving - Realize that students with special needs has a special potential
Feel not being a good friend	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Often yell to students with special needs - Often ask students with special needs to carry heavy group's things on. - Have not been able to reciprocate students with special needs's kindness - Lack of attention - Have not been a partner that could give some solutions

Intention is one's conscience. Based on the theory of moral development viewed from the theory of learning, the conscience is a system of norms that have been internalized (into a private property) so that the behavior as same as what should be done and not based on punishment or other reinforcement (Rita Ekka Izzaty, 2008: 149). Intention or conscience is based on a sense of friendship that does not distinguish and a sense of affection towards students with special needs.

Mulyono Abdurahman (Tarmansyah, 2007: 37) explains that the symbol of the Bhineka Tunggal Ika embodies the recognition of human diversity. This diversity includes vertical diversity (differences in intelligence, physical strength, financial ability, rank, self-control) and horizontal (ethnic, racial, linguistic, cultural, religious, residential, regional, political affiliation) differences. These differences should not be separated from each other including between children with special needs with ordinary humans.

The student's initiative in helping is a natural consciousness that comes from thoughts and feelings so that consider as meaningful. Regular students understand the weaknesses of students with special needs that require assistance. These weaknesses make regular students feel relied upon to overcome their difficulties at school.

Meanwhile, the low acceptance is caused by a low understanding as follows.

Table 10: Factors from Outside of Students with Special Needs Who Credited Reception

Aspect	Data
Have a Low Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students with special needs is less concentrated in lessons so often fails - Has no potential - Has the same characteristics - Think late so that hampers the group - Disturb friends' learning because teachers have to repeat the subject explanation

Some students who have a low understanding of students with special needs will doubt the potential of students with special needs in activities.

Meanwhile, the teacher's and Headmaster's mindset affecting the high acceptance of students with special needs is listed in the following table.

Table 11: Teachers' Mindset, Employee, and Headmaster

Aspect	Data
Teachers who Understand Students with Special Needs is Unique	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deliver the materials slowly - Characteristics of them depends on the nature - Students with special needs can have high IQ, but some are not and limited - Needs guidance in communication - Give the opportunity to develop their potential
Every human is different	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers understand that they has a different character and potential from regular students
Inclusion According to Principles of Education and the 1945 Constitution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers understand Education has principles of equality, similarity, and there is no difference. - The teacher understands inclusion in accordance with the 1945 Constitution (every citizen should be served without discrimination)
Aspect	Data
Teachers Believe in Moral	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People must be beneficial to others - They do not put any difficulties to others.
Teachers Understand School Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students with special needs is a part of the school

	so there is no reason not to accept them.
Teachers Understand the Benefits of Inclusion for Schools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students are more responsible and grateful - Teachers are more aware of the condition and development of them - Students could be more patient and do good things - Teacher's curiosity will be more encouraged in handling them
Headmaster Understands that Students with Special Needs, Needs Different Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intensifely in delivering the material - The materials' target and comprehension are easier - Schools do not provide maximum service to serve with conscience
Headmaster Understands and Receive Students with Special Needs according to the Meaning of Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Differences within the inclusion school are kept to a minimum scale even the differences as if aren't seen. - Inclusion aims to unite all students so that all can mingle, socialize, and appreciate - The rights and obligations of all students are equal
The "Among" System Concerning the Concept of Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education should liberate the child so that all students are equal, handled and educated without being distinguished - The "among" system means that the teachers should be able to guide the students and at the same time, they act as the parents of the student, so that the students can develop in terms of heart, independence, skill, and knowledge.
Inclusion Relating to Objectives of Tamansiswa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tamansiswa is a university that is universal for all people which roles out the background, personality, nature, behavior, or level of IQ - There are about 1-3 registered students with special needs in every class. - Schools receive them with the aim of encouraging regular students' empathy to blend in and help others

Based on the information in the table above, the equation of treatment by teachers is based on the understanding that students with special needs as same as students in SMP Taman Matur Ibu Pawiyatan and equality as human being. This difference is based on the different needs between students with special needs and regular students. Some of the characteristics that should be developed from the school model of "Equally and Friendly School For All" is to understand that everyone should not be treated equally and schools provide services for children according to their needs (Dapa in Jopyy Liando & Aldio Dapa, 2007: 136). Teachers also understand the characteristics of students with special needs that are different and have the potential to be explored so that they need the opportunity to develop their potential. Kirk and Gallagher (Muljono

Abdurrachman and Sudjaji, 1994: 9) define children with special needs as children who diverge from the average or normal children in: (1) mental characteristics, (2) sensory abilities, (3) neuromotor or physical characteristics, (4) social behavior, (5) communication skills, and (6) a combination of these variables.

In addition to the above information, there are teachers who are not too able to accept the students with special needs due to inconvenience of teaching the students with special needs that have a low understanding. The teachers think that dealing with students with special needs need a lot of energy and thought, since the number is increased while the priority of the teacher is still on the regular students. This will only cause stress and failure of the teacher if their teaching skills are less in dealing with students. Lay Kekeh Marthan (2007: 176) states teachers who teach in inclusive classes with different students in the physical, intellectual, social, emotional, and / or neurological sensoryists should apply the general principles of learning and implement specific principles according to needs of the students.

Meanwhile, the Headmaster understands the rights and obligations of all students are same. Rafika Rahmawati (2012: 6) explains that in every inclusive schools, children is cultivated to get optimal service by performing various modifications and or adjustments starting from curriculum, facilities and infrastructure, educator and education, learning system, to the scoring system. However, in the implementation, the teachers have not compiled the PPI (Individual Learning Program) which allows the students with special needs to get the material according to their ability. Schools are aware that they can not provide maximum services such as facilities, IEP (Individual Educational Program), talent development and potential, teachers' controls, etc.

In addition, acceptance is based because Tamansiswa is open up for all people which rules out the background, personality, nature, behavior, or IQ level. Some teachers considered that inclusion education has a correlation with Among system that is carried by Ki Hadjar Dewantara as a method of education at Perguruan Tamansiswa. Inclusion includes students with different needs. Muhammad Nur Wangid (2009: 133) explains the understanding of the system among is that the Among system requires the teacher to remember and emphasize the children's nature, by not forgetting any circumstances.

The concept of inclusion is also similar with the vision of Tamansiswa that is "Achievement in Science and Technology, Leading in Culture and Glorious Art in Character". The virtue of character is the key to the formation of inclusiveness. Hermanto et al (2013: 16) explains that inclusive education manages not to discriminate against children with special needs in obtaining humane treatment, quality education according to the potential and assertion of society.

e. Hope

The next factor is the expectation of students with special needs. These expectations are listed in the following table.

Table 12: Students, Teachers, Employee, and Headmaster Expectations on the Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
Students' Hope to Students with Special Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - be indeoendent, settle more, not being arrogant - Maturity and confidence are increased - Make friends with everyone - Minggle with regular students, not to cluster with students with special needs only - Recovered well, success - Add more teachers with shadow teacher
Teachers' Expectations and Employees' to Students with Special Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Find and develop talent and potential better. - Be responsible for their life by growing their independence - advance their study at inclusive schools that facilitate the needs and talents of students.
Teachers' Expectations and Employees' To School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do a home visit - Improve communication with students with special needs - Increase empathy
Teachers' and Employees' Expectations to Countries and Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides better access for person with disabilities - Persons with disabilities are treated well by society and not to be underestimated.
Headmaster' Expectations to Students with Special Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students with special needs can live independently. - Students with special needs be able more to develop their potential

Regular students accept students with special needs with the aim that students with special needs will do better in terms of personality, attitudes, emotions, and social interaction to achieve environmental adjustment and independence. Expectations by teachers, employees, and headmaster are ment to be familiar with and understand the characteristics of students with special needs so they can give the best service to grow the potential of the students with special needs. Victor Vroom summons a theory called "Theory of Hope" which asserts that, "*motivation is the result of an outcome achieved by a person and the estimation that his actions will lead to the desired outcomes.*" (Sarinah and Mardalena, 2017: 90).

f. Parents' Influence

The influence of social status and the doctrine by students with special needs' parents are listed in the following table.

Table 13: Parents' Influence of Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
Having a High Social Status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parents always accompany them so it will be making them to carry group items easier. - Regular students want to be close to the parents who work as the students dream to.

- Regular students have ever asked for snacks to them
 - Parents of students with special needs pay more attention to school so the school will respond automatically and more attentionfully.
-

Some regular students claim to be happy to involve students with special needs whose their parents have a higher social status. They have a help in carrying out group assignments, earning a profit, gaining knowledge from the parents of students with specials about the dreams and ideals. Hurlock (in Rita Eka Izzaty, et al, 2008: 142), one of the factors that affecting adolescent social acceptance is about the same or slightly higher social status of the group and a good relationship with their family. Meanwhile, the special attention given by schools is a positive response from students with special needs parents' attention to the school so feedback accurs between the two.

However, low acceptance is also influenced by parents who indoctrinate their children with special needs (initial DM) to not be friends with other students with special needs because they consider their children not including one of them. Regular students are less likely and close to the DM because of that doctrine. Many factors come from families that affect individual such as parental education level, economic level, relationship between the parents work, family attitudes overcome social issues, reality, etc., that will give experiences to the children and thought in interest, appreciation, attitude, economic understanding, language vocabulary, communication ability with others, point of view, speaking style, and how to make a cooperative relationships with others. (Oemar Hamalik, 2001: 182)

g. Social Resentment

The social resentment of regular students who consider that students with special needs is treated special will be one of the factors of influencing the low acceptance. Regular students question the attitudes of students with special needs who often be late at classes, and they do not get a punishment, in other hand they just get a warning. Tauchid in 50 Years Taman Siswa (in Muhammad Nur Wangid, 2009: 133) explains the reason why teachers give warning or reprimand because it refers to the teachings rules of Tamansiswa. Punishment should not be given if it tortures students. It should be as a redeemer of mistakes. While the use of command and coercion should only be done when the students can not avoid the danger that will befall it with their own strength. (Muhammad Nur Wangid, 2009: 133). This may be the reason why teachers rarely give a firmer warning to the students with special needs who often be late at classes.

The acceptance in a school is not entirely high. The low acceptance forms that occurred at SMP Taman Matur Ibu Pawiyatan are listed in the following table.

Table 14: Low Acceptance to Students with Special Needs

Aspect	Data
Regular Students' Low Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not to be close friends and not able when they are needed - Students with special needs is less fond - When students with special needs was confused to answer teacher questions, they will be pleased.
Regular Students' Low Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students with special needs' trivial questions are made into a laughing stock - They do not make a friend with everybody - Be angry and yelled often at Students with special needs
Regular Students' Low Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A deaf students are considered stingy and arrogant - When students with special needs do not lend them their stuff, they will be irritated. - Mocking with inappropriate words - Throwing off student with special needs' shoes - Ignoring - Mocking and bringing them into conflict - Staying away of students with special needs - Regular students complain when students with special needs ask the teachers to repeat the material in class - Calling student with special needs as ABK (initial) - Not be in the same group with them - Pushing and hitting the
Teachers' Low Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers can not control themselves well to teach students with special needs
School Low Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blind students cannot enroll the school due to limited human resources - Rejected students with special needs are suggested to Special School - Students with special needs quota as a new student is limited because of limited teacher staff.

The information above shows that low acceptance of students with special needs occurs in the form of verbal, treatment, and emotion. However, in inclusive schools there should be reduced a rejection or low acceptance, because the inclusive schools are heterogeneous to the students' abilities and conditions. Therefore, students with special needs and schools need to act in supporting the acceptance of students with special needs.

Table 15: Acceptance Supporting Efforts

Aspect	Data
Actively Associated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students with special needs to actively approach their friends
Students with Special Needs are Able to Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do not take it seriously when a friend gives jokes

Emotions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploding the emotions in their house - Apologizing after being reprimanded - They are not easily to be angry
Students with Special Needs are Able to Control Emotions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be calm down by avoiding when they do inappropriate behaviors - Holding emotions and feelings - Talkless and do not do things that are prohibited in class - Apologize after doing mistakes and explain about the misdeeds - Obey the commands given
Special Assistance Effort	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Giving the students regular understanding not to hate and make friends with the students with special needs - Guiding students to obey the school rules - Guiding students to do appropriate behavior only - Instilling obedience students
School' Special Facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a sloping road with a handle and a wheelchair for students with a quadriplegic
Shadow Teacher (Shadower)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 shadow teacher appointed by school - There is a shadower independently hired by student's parents
The existence of additional courses for students with special needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of them separated courses in graders VII and VIII - Implementation of them combined courses in graders IX
Cooperative class through working group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students choose their own co-worker group - Teacher decides the groups in several ways e.g., sweepstakes, sorting the students based on their student number and student's position.
Socialization of students with special needs to students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Socialization is done through orientation school about inclusive schools
Teacher competency improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers attend seminars, training and workshops on students with special needs handling
Use of Government Assistance and Parent Funds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of government assistance (provision of workshops and seminars for teachers and parents of students with special needs) - Additional Courses procurement with monthly fund Rp 250.000,

Students with special needs need to improve their ability to get closer to their friends so that regular students are expected to be able to accept and understand them. Emotional control effort is done so that the behavior of students with special needs follows the environmental values in Tamansiswa in order to prevent the undesirable emotions among students. According to Waluyo et al, (2008: 50) factors that influences the process of someone's socialization are the basic behaviour that includes character, nature, and emotional behaviour; prenatal environment; individual differences; environment; and motivation.

Special escort role is needed in behaviour control. Dedy Kustawan (2012: 79) states the role of shadower not only assisting students with special needs during the learning activities but also bridging the instruction between teachers and the students, controlling behavior and interaction, concentrating, and informing the postponed lesson.

Meanwhile, the facilities and services for students with special needs in SMP Taman Dewasa (autism, slow learner, deaf, and mental disorder) are lack. It can be seen that most of regular students use those facilities, and services. One of the available facilities is aquadabic facility and it can be used well because there are not students with a quadriplegic. The school has a shadow teacher that can help to improve the acceptance of the students with special needs. Wahyu Sri Ambar (2009: 86-87) explains shadow teacher who visited the school or class provide to offer a help, as a consultant for the classroom teacher / field of study, and provide special services for children with special needs. Special course as a remedial is also useful for students with special needs. Sunaryo Kartadinata (2002: 56) suggests that students who have learning problems require special services (courses) by teachers outside the learning process situation.

The teacher's effort to engage students with special needs in class activities is also through cooperative learning with the formation of working groups. Slavin (In Pipih Suherti, 2011: 44) explains that cooperative learning is a set of learning methods that organize children to work together in doing academic tasks in small groups with different abilities. A cooperative learning enables students to interact and to be fenceless to achieve common goals.

Socialization efforts towards regular students aims to improve the understanding of regular students in dealing with and interacting with students with special needs so that the acceptance will be implemented. Seminars, training, and workshops that are joined by teachers aim to support the knowledge of teachers in providing optimal services for students with special needs. Assistance provided by the government such as the procurement of workshops and seminars for teachers and parents with students with special needs are meant to improve the competency.

5. Recomaendation

5.1 For School

- 1) Regular students, teachers, employees, and Headmasters could enhance interaction with students with special needs to be more open and understanding the characteristics of students with special needs so that they could be more confident.
- 2) Students with special needs should improve and maintain social activities to get involved in common activities and not stepping out, and control the emotions in social activities school.
- 3) The special teacher needs to enhance and maintain the efforts that has been undertaken in the acceptance towards the students. One of them is to establish a

behaviour to fit the school environment. They also coach regular students and students with special needs to always be friends and work together.

- 4) Schools needs to improve special facilities such as learning media for students with special needs such as students with mental disorder, slow learning, and autism so that the students are more easily to get involved in learning activities
- 5) School needs to consider special teacher in providing services to students with special needs, remedial for students with special needs, cooperative class, socialization about students with special needs in school environment, and accessing funds from government and parents of students with special needs for the needs of the students.

5.2 For Further Researchers

- 1) Researchers are expected to learn and find more information from sources or references about the school acceptance and the factors influencing towards students with special needs completely and accurately.
- 2) Researchers is able to train himself to be more skillful in order to collect the data, so that it can be more notable.

6. Conclusion

- a. Regular students' acceptance towards students with special needs occurs in choosing as a partner and work groups in class activities, being close friends, talking and joking, and making partners in joint activities.
- b. teachers and employees' acceptance towards students with special needs occurs in the equality of social treatment, close relationships, involvement in class activities, offering helps with special cares and greetings.
- c. The Headmaster's acceptance towards students with special needs occurs in the greetings, protection from threats, and involvement in maintaining the school environment.
- d. Factors of acceptance towards students with special needs that consider to a high acceptance are normal physical ; the way to dress up suits to the school environment; good social behavior includes the ability of cooperation, responsibility, good attitude especially in talking, lack of distracting and mocking , and interact with regular students; has special potential; a good and positive personality like honest, extrovert, not being arrogant, stingy, lazy, and spoiled; and have mature emotions.
- e. Factors of acceptance from outside of student with special needs that consider to a high acceptance are the first impression; high Empathy; positive personality e.g.,compassionate, friendly, patient, assertive, willing to understand conditions of students with special needs, positive thinking toward others, and extrovert; good mindset; good hope; parental high status; there is no social resentment

between regular students with students with special needs; and there is no provision as a form of parental doctrine.

6.1 Research Findings

- a. Students with special needs are confident and able to interact socially with regular students if the school environment understands their needs and accepts in any form of activity.
- b. Students with special needs efforts to be accepted in the school environment are about to be active to make friends and able to control the emotions.
- c. Special teacher efforts in supporting the acceptance is to instill students with special needs compliance, behavioral suitability, and guide the perception and understanding of regular students to interact with students with special needs.
- d. School effort to support the acceptance is providing special facilities, special teacher, shadow teacher, remedial courses, cooperative learning through working groups, socialization activities to regular students about students with special needs, teacher competence improvement, and the use of government assistance and parents funds of the students with special needs to meet the needs of students.

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